
Curiosity Unleashed: The Power of Inquiry-Based Learning

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Summary— The innovation titled "Curiosity Unleashed: The Power of Inquiry-Based Learning" by Chrislie Joy P. Posadas aims to address the challenges learners face in creating Science Investigatory Projects (SIPs) by fostering critical thinking and scientific inquiry through an inquiry-based learning (IBL) approach. This methodology emphasizes student-centered learning, where students actively engage in exploring, experimenting, and problem-solving. By incorporating the five general phases of inquiry—Orientation, Conceptualization, Investigation, Conclusion, and Discussion—students are guided through structured scientific discovery, enhancing their analytical and research skills. The implementation of IBL in the curriculum not only prepares students for academic success but also equips them with essential skills for future careers and real-world applications. The innovation has demonstrated an 83% effectiveness rate, with significant improvements in students' critical thinking, problem-solving, and scientific literacy. This approach aligns with the educational mission of empowering learners and fostering a lifelong passion for learning and exploration.

Keywords— Curriculum Innovation, Inquiry-Based Learning, Science Investigatory Projects, Critical Thinking, Scientific Inquiry

I. OVERVIEW

Many learners often encounter difficulties when it comes to crafting a Science Investigatory Project (SIP), grappling with the formulation of hypotheses, execution of experiments, and the proficient analysis of gathered data. However, mastering the SIP process is not merely about overcoming these challenges; it's about nurturing critical thinking skills essential for problem analysis, hypothesis development, and experiment design. Through this journey, students not only enhance their scientific literacy but also cultivate a profound confidence in their ability to navigate the intricacies of scientific inquiry, all while gaining practical experience in applying scientific principles to real-world scenarios. By empowering learners to take an active role in their education, inquiry-based learning not only fosters essential skills such as problem-solving, collaboration, and creativity but also instills a lifelong passion for learning and exploration. This approach supports the Department's Mission and embodies the ethos of "Empowering Learners, Building Futures." The innovation of exploring inquiry-based learning as an approach to unleash the learners' curiosity led to the making of a Science Investigatory Project (SIP). This addresses the distress of teachers caused by the annual sci-tech expo in selecting learners who will represent the SIP event. By honing essential research and analytical skills, proficiency in SIPs lays a robust foundation for students to excel in their chosen paths,

equipped with the tools necessary to tackle complex challenges and contribute meaningfully to the scientific community. Moreover, inquiry-based learning catalyzes students to develop the requisite skills, knowledge, and mindset to undertake meaningful and successful SIPs. By providing a solid foundation rooted in inquiry and exploration, students are empowered to delve into the depths of scientific inquiry with confidence, paving the way for transformative discoveries and innovations that shape the future of science and technology. Based on Pedaste et al., (2015) perspective, as derived from the synthesized framework, includes five general inquiry phases: Orientation, Conceptualization, Investigation, Conclusion, and Discussion. These phases represent the essential stages involved in the process of scientific discovery and knowledge construction. The framework effectively encapsulates the core elements of inquiry-based learning, aligning with the author's dedication to promoting active participation, critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and a deep understanding of scientific concepts

II. INNOVATION DESCRIPTION

Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL) stands out as an innovative teaching methodology that revolutionizes traditional education paradigms by placing the student at the forefront of the learning journey. Through IBL, students are no longer passive recipients of information, but active participants engaged in exploration, experimentation, and problem-solving. Central to IBL is the cultivation of critical thinking skills through the presentation of open-ended questions or challenges that encourage students to delve deep, analyze infor-

mation critically, and synthesize their conclusions.

This student-centered approach is facilitated by educators who act as guides, providing resources and support as students navigate their inquiries. Collaboration among peers is fostered, promoting communication, teamwork, and peer learning. Hands-on activities and projects provide tangible experiences that solidify abstract concepts, while structured inquiry processes mirror real-world research methods, instilling valuable research skills applicable across disciplines. Reflection and metacognition are encouraged, allowing students to gain insights into their learning processes and preferences. Assessment in IBL is authentic, measuring students' understanding and growth in real-world contexts through projects, presentations, and performance tasks. Ultimately, IBL aims to equip students with lifelong learning skills, nurturing curiosity, initiative, and adaptability, thus preparing them to thrive in today's ever-evolving society.

III. INNOVATION STATEMENT

Inquiry-based learning aims to cultivate a dynamic educational environment where students are actively engaged in the exploration of knowledge.

At its core, this approach seeks to nurture curiosity, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills. By encouraging students to ask questions, investigate topics, and seek out answers through inquiry and experimentation, the goal is to foster a deep understanding of concepts and phenomena. Through this process, students develop the ability to think independently, analyze information, and make informed decisions.

Additionally, inquiry-based learning promotes collaboration and communication skills as students work together to explore complex issues and share their findings. By connecting learning to real-world contexts and encouraging creativity and innovation, this approach not only prepares students for academic success but also equips them with the tools and mindset necessary to navigate and contribute to a rapidly evolving global society.

Ultimately, the objectives of inquiry-based learning are to inspire a lifelong love of learning, cultivate self-directed learners, and empower individuals to become active participants in their education and the world around them.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION PROCEDURE

a. Process Flow Framework

Inquiry-based learning follows five general phases that guide students through a structured process of exploration and discovery. By following these five phases – Orientation, Conceptualization, Investigation, Conclusion, and Discussion – students develop critical thinking skills, deepen their understanding of scientific concepts, and become active participants in their learning journey through inquiry-based learning.

First, the Orientation phase introduces students to the topic or problem they will investigate, sparking their curiosity and interest. Here, teachers may pose thought-provoking questions, show relevant videos, or conduct discussions to engage students and set the stage for inquiry. Second, is the Conceptualization phase, students deepen their understanding of the

topic by exploring key concepts, vocabulary, and background information. Teachers may provide resources, demonstrations, or guided activities to help students build foundational knowledge and develop hypotheses or initial ideas.

Third, the Investigation phase is where students actively engage in hands-on experimentation, data collection, and analysis. They design and conduct experiments, make observations, record data, and draw conclusions based on evidence. Teachers facilitate inquiry by providing guidance, materials, and support as students explore their questions and test their hypotheses. Fourth, in the Conclusion phase, students reflect on their findings and draw conclusions based on the evidence gathered during the investigation. They analyze their data, identify patterns or trends, and evaluate the validity of their hypotheses. Teachers encourage students to communicate their findings through written reports, presentations, or visual displays.

Finally, the Discussion phase provides an opportunity for students to share and discuss their findings, insights, and challenges with peers. They engage in collaborative dialogue, critique each other's work, and reflect on the inquiry process. Teachers facilitate discussions to help students make connections between their findings and broader scientific concepts or real-world applications.

b. Project Management

Managing inquiry-based learning innovation requires a comprehensive approach involving educators, administrators, and students to foster an environment conducive to active, experiential learning. This collaborative effort is crucial for the successful implementation and sustainability of this approach, enabling all learners to engage in individual or group investigatory projects.

To facilitate the effective execution of this innovation, project management strategies are employed. Clear goals and objectives are established, outlining what learners aim to achieve through their investigatory projects. Detailed timelines and milestones are set to track progress and ensure timely completion. Resources are allocated efficiently, including necessary materials, support, and guidance from educators and administrators. Regular progress reviews and evaluations are conducted to monitor the implementation process and identify areas for improvement.

Educators play a pivotal role in guiding learners through the innovation process. They ensure that students understand and follow the inquiry-based learning approach, providing necessary support and feedback to facilitate progress. Through this structured framework, learners are empowered to develop and write their Science Investigatory Projects (SIP), leveraging the skills and knowledge gained from their experiential learning experiences. This hands-on approach not only enhances students' academic capabilities but also cultivates essential skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration. By embracing inquiry-based learning, educators and administrators can create a dynamic educational environment that nurtures curiosity, creativity, and lifelong learning among students.

Fig. 1: Innovation Flow

c. Timeline

Managing the inquiry-based learning innovation involves integrating the five general inquiry phases—Orientation, Conceptualization, Investigation, Conclusion, and Discussion—into a structured framework that guides students through the process of scientific discovery and knowledge construction. These phases are fundamental to fostering active participation, critical thinking, and a deep understanding of scientific concepts.

In the pre-implementation stage, which spans two months at the beginning of the school year, learners engage in orientation and conceptualization. This period focuses on introducing the research objectives and establishing a conceptual foundation for their scientific inquiries.

During the implementation stage, which falls under the Investigation phase and lasts for one month, students delve into research methods and design, applying their understanding to conduct investigative work.

Post-implementation activities, occurring in the second quarter of the school year over two months, revolve around the Conclusion and Discussion phases. Here, learners analyze and discuss research results, draw conclusions, and formulate recommendations based on their science investigatory project (SIP) findings.

Moreover, the effectiveness of this approach was evaluated through Action Research, which collected data to support its efficacy. This assessment highlighted successful execution, resulting in the completion of several science investigatory projects. By integrating these phases and conducting ongoing assessments, educators and administrators can optimize the inquiry-based learning experience, nurtur-

ing students’ scientific inquiry skills and fostering meaningful learning outcomes.

d. Resource Utilization

The innovation of inquiry-based learning utilizes a range of primary resources crucial for guiding learners through the research process effectively. These resources include laptops, an LED TV for presentations, internet connectivity, and handouts, which are integral during the orientation and conceptualization stages of research. Learners are introduced to experimental methods early in the school year, gradually progressing towards independent research projects, aligning with the five general phases of inquiry-based learning.

In the pre-implementation phase, focused on orientation and conceptualization, teachers leverage these resources to provide foundational guidance. Throughout the implementation phase, access to the internet—available in the ICT room or through public Wi-Fi within the school—is essential for conducting research and gathering information.

During post-implementation, learners interpret and finalize their research findings. Initially, the development phase necessitates printing of science investigatory project (SIP) drafts, utilizing paper resources. Iterative adjustments may require reprinting, but once a final design is achieved, subsequent printings become unnecessary, optimizing resource efficiency.

This resource-conscious approach ensures that learners have the necessary tools and guidance to navigate each phase of the inquiry-based learning process effectively. By leveraging these resources strategically, educators can facilitate meaningful scientific exploration while minimizing unne-

essary resource consumption.

e. Progress Monitoring

The teacher plays a pivotal role in overseeing the implementation of the inquiry-based learning innovation to ensure its effectiveness in guiding students through the process of writing a Science Investigatory Project (SIP). This monitoring process involves regular assessment of teaching practices, student engagement, and learning outcomes using observation checklists, student surveys, and performance assessments. By following the five general phases of inquiry-based learning, the teacher tracks learners' progress and maintains detailed records of scores, observations, and feedback.

These records serve as valuable tools for monitoring student development, identifying areas for improvement, and refining inquiry-based teaching methods. A total of 35 SIPs outputs were successfully generated, reflecting an 83% effectiveness rate of this innovation. The primary beneficiaries of this approach are Grade 6 learners who engage in the science investigatory project process, benefiting from the structured support and guidance provided through the inquiry-based learning framework.

V. SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

I am committed to consistently integrating Inquiry-based Learning into my teaching practices by reintroducing it to my students annually, ensuring that more students can benefit from its use. Each year, I will compile Science Investigatory Projects (SIP) to make them readily available for learners, teachers, educational officials, and stakeholders, showcasing the benefits of this innovative approach from learners' perspectives.

By reintroducing the innovation yearly and maintaining accessibility, there is consistent support, reducing the risk of discontinuity and preserving its effectiveness over time. I will actively seek feedback from teachers and students to make necessary improvements, refining processes and adding supplementary resources to enhance learning experiences. Collaborating with educational experts and researchers will provide insights into innovative teaching methodologies and practices, continuously improving the innovation's impact.

To sustain the use of inquiry-based learning in science investigatory projects, future actions will focus on fostering a culture of inquiry-based learning, providing ongoing support and resources, and integrating project-based learning into the curriculum to promote continued engagement and innovation in scientific exploration.

Furthermore, implementing mentorship programs, facilitating interdisciplinary collaborations, and incorporating real-world applications can deepen students' understanding, creativity, and problem-solving skills. This approach not only enhances the outcomes of science investigatory projects but also fosters critical thinking, scientific literacy, and curiosity among students, contributing to innovation, advancing scientific knowledge, and addressing real-world challenges through student-led research and experimentation.

Outputs/Outcomes <i>(enumerates the outputs or outcomes produced from this innovation)</i>	Beneficiaries <i>(who benefited from the corresponding results of outcomes)</i>
Critical Thinking Skills Personal Growth and Confidence Preparation for Future Careers Real-World Relevance Curiosity and Interest in Science Creativity and Innovation Scientific Literacy	Students
Problem-Solving Skills Compilation of Science Investigatory Project (SIP)	Teachers Schools and Educational Institutions

Fig. 2: Outputs/Outcomes

REFERENCES

Pedaste, M., Mäeots, M., Siiman, L. A., De Jong, T., Van Riesen, S. A., Kamp, E. T., & Tsourlidaki, E. (2015). Phases of inquiry-based learning: Definitions and the inquiry cycle. *Educational Research Review, 14*, 47–61.

VI. APPENDICES

Fig. 3: Means of Verification